

Indigoid Vat Dyes of the Isatin Series. Part XII. 3-Indole-2'-(7'-bromo)thionaphthene Indigos

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A few 3-indole-2'-(7'-bromo)thionaphthene indigos have been synthesised by condensing 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene with different isatins. These are found lighter in colour than those of the corresponding 5'-bromo dyes, previously studied.

Some attractive violet-red 3-indole-2'-(5'-bromo)thionaphthene indigos were reported by Guha and Banerji¹. In this communication the preparation of another class of 3-indole-2'-(7'-bromo)thionaphthene indigos are described along with their various properties. 3-Hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene was condensed with various isatins to obtain the corresponding thioindigoid dyes, represented by the general structure (I)

The dyes of this 7'-bromo series are light-brown, brown-violet, dark-violet, and reddish-violet crystalline products. The first dye (I) is a nonshining substance, but the rest possess a beautiful sparkling appearance. Their yield range from 70-88%. These are soluble in nitrobenzene, aniline and toluene; moderately soluble in acetic acid except the dibromo dye (VI) which is only sparingly soluble; slightly soluble in chloroform, benzene, and xylene; almost insoluble in ethanol. On treatment with strong sulphuric acid and slightly warmed these dyes produce uniform violet solution.

The dyed shades developed on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat at 70° are uniform but not so deep and bright as that of the colour of the compounds themselves. The nitro dyes (V, VII, and VIII) produced a deep-yellow vat, whereas the colour of the vat of the remaining dyes is yellow. An examination of colour, dyed shade, and absorption maxima data (Table I) of some of the 7'-, and 5'-bromo dyes² lead to the conclusion that 7'-bromo dyes are lighter in colour.

1. *This Journal*, 1953, 30, 820.

2. Guha *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1960, 93, 1925.

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TABLE I

Dyes	Reactants	Colour & appearance	Shade on cotton	Yield	Formula	Found	Reqd.
(I) 3-Indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	Isatin (0.073g.) HBT (0.115g.) AcOH (25ml)	Light brown needles turning darkish brown-violet on scrubbing.	Light brown	80%	$C_{16}H_6O_2NBrS$	C: 53.31% H: 2.14	53.64 2.25
(II) 3-(5-Chloro)indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	5-chloro-isatin (0.18g) HBT(0.23g.) AcOH (40 ml)	Brown-violet	Brown-violet	84	$C_{16}H_5ClO_2NBrS$	N: 3.71	3.56
(III) 3-(6-Bromo)indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	6-Bromo-isatin (0.115g.) HBT (0.115g.) AcOH(25 ml)	Brown-violet crystals	Do	76	$C_{16}H_5O_2NBr_2S$	C: 44.06 H: 1.59	43.96 1.61
(IV) 3-(6-Iodo)indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	5-Iodo-isatin(0.273g.) HBT (0.229g.)	Do	Do (but more deep than I & II)	80	$C_{16}H_4O_2NBrIS$	C: 39.72 H: 1.85	39.69 1.45
(V) 3-(5-Nitro)indole-3'-(7-bromo)-I	5-Nitro-isatin (0.102g.) HBT (0.229g.)	Dark violet needles	Do (darkish)	88	$C_{16}H_5O_2N_2BrS$	N: 7.28	6.83
(VI) 3-(5,7-Dibromo)-indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	5, 7-Dibromo-isatin (0.305g.) HBT(0.229g.) AcOH (50 ml)	Brown-violet needles	Brown-violet	76	$C_{16}H_4O_2NBr_3S$	C: 37.61 H: 1.11	37.33 1.17
(VII) 3-(6-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	5-Bromo-7-nitro isatin (0.27g.) HBT (0.229g.) AcOH	Brown-violet crystals	Do (darkish)	70	$C_{16}H_4O_4N_2Br_2S$	N: 6.23	5.81
(VIII) 3-(5,7-Dinitro)-indole-3'-(7'-bromo)-I	5,7-Dinitro-indole (0.237g.) HBT(0.229g.) AcOH (50 ml)	Reddish violet needles	Do (more deep than VII)	86	$C_{16}H_4O_6N_3BrS$	N: 8.95	9.37

*I denotes thionaphthene indigo

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The 7'-bromo dyes were prepared in glacial acetic acid medium in the same manner as the 5'-bromo dyes and finally crystallised from nitrobenzene, not melting below 300°. The absorption maxima were determined in xylene solution. The values are recorded in Table II. For convenience HBT denotes 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene. The eight

TABLE II

		λ_{max}
3-I-2'-(7'-Bromo)-T	..	508 m μ
3-I-2'-(5'-Bromo)-T	..	516
3-(6,7 -Dibromo)-I-2'-(7'-Bromo)-T	..	512
3-(5,7 -Dibromo)-I-2'-5'-(Bromo)-T	..	522
3-(5,7 -Dinitro)-I-2'-(7'-Bromo)-T	..	523
3-(5,7-Dinitro)-I-2'-(5'-Bromo)-T	..	528

T denotes thionaphthene indigo and I, indole.

dyes prepared are recorded in Table I. 3-Indole-2'-(7'-bromo)thionaphthene indigo(I) was obtained from isatin (0.07g) and HBT (0.115g).

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